

PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE METHODOLOGY OF QUALIFICATION OF CRIME AND PUNISHMENT

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Abstract: In the article, the specific features, necessity, and actuality of the concepts of crime and punishment were researched, and in this process, its socio-philosophical, moral, spiritual, legal classification and specific features were analyzed.

Key words: crime, punishment, historical development of crime, criminal law, elimination of crime, liberalization, socio-anthropological characteristics.

INTRODUCTION

The classification of crime and punishment should be based on the use of a synthesized complex of various knowledge and methods reflected in the socio-legal model of the prohibition of criminal law in the process of understanding criminal behavior. Modern methodologies of perception show the relevance of the use and achievements of philosophical hermeneutics, phenomenology, whose categorical apparatus can be adapted to improve the epistemological means of qualifying a crime in accordance with the functions of criminal-legal regulation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Specific features of the concepts of crime and punishment, general theoretical issues of qualification I.V. Andreev, N.A. Babi, L.D. Gauxman, A.A. Hertsenzon, V.V. Kolosovsky, A.V. Korneeva, V.N. Kudryavtsev, N.F. Kuznetsova, B.A. Kurinov, V. Navitsky, V. Navitsky, K.V.Obrazhieva, N.I.Panova, A.I.Raroga, R.A.Sabitova, V.Y.Tatsiya, S.A.Tararukhina, A.A.Tolkachenko and other researchers have studied in detail.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Philosophical-methodological principles of the qualification of crime and punishment have the meaning of postulating ideas that determine the general direction of the cognitive process based on the main branches of philosophical knowledge: ontology, axiology and epistemology.

The principles of special qualification describe the specific features of knowledge in the process of socio-legal assessment of the committed criminal act. In the spectrum of different and conflicting doctrinal positions, it has been proved that a separate principle of crime qualification should include an independent provision for social-legal assessment describing the order of comparative responsibility for the crime committed. . Based on this, the author's concept of the

types of special principles of qualification of crime and punishment is determined by the principles of comparability, scientificity, sufficiency and interpretation of irrefutable doubts in favor of the accused.

However, scientists who have addressed this issue (V.N. Kudryavtsev, R.A. Sabitov, A.A. Tolkachenko) mainly consider the epistemological essence of the process of applying the criminal law norm to a specific and general situation in the context of the relationship between the person and the philosophical categories of the person. Undoubtedly, the dialectical method of knowledge is important in the process of qualifying crime and punishment, especially in the period of collecting and evaluating factual information. At the same time, legal scholars cannot ignore the changes taking place in the methodology of knowledge. It should be taken into account that currently a critical revision of the classical paradigm is being carried out in the philosophical theory of knowledge, which should predetermine the methodology of legal knowledge. Many jurists began to actively use other cognitive approaches and mental methods to understand legal situations in understanding legal reality (S.I. Maksimov, V.I. Pavlov, A.V. Polyakov, A.V. Stovba, I.L. Chestnov). The use of such methods presupposes the presence of a lawyer in the legal reality of all legal events, including not only "legal events", but also any events of legal significance, in particular, a crime.

In various literature, the concept of criminal-legal situation is given, which is described as a conflict situation caused by a socially dangerous act, in which authorized persons must make a socio-legal assessment of the act committed in the current legal reality. It is shown that the non-classical methodology of perception offers different ways of studying the relevant components of legal reality. In our opinion, different philosophical approaches should be used to understand the qualification of crime and punishment. Currently, the methodological experience gathered within the framework of philosophical hermeneutics and phenomenology is of scientific and practical interest.

In addition, a synopsis of the main studies on philosophical hermeneutics (H.G. Gadamer, W. Dilthey, M. Heidegger, F. Schleiermacher) and phenomenology (E. Husserl, P. Riquier) is given, which shows how important their experience is in the cognitive process. 'shown. E. Husserl's idea of the intentional attitude of our mind to the surrounding reality expands the field of hermeneutics and allows consideration of hermeneutic procedures and methods not only related to the understanding and interpretation of the text of the criminal law.

Since law enforcement activities are cognitive in nature, the modern works of many philosophers and jurists focus on legal hermeneutics (E.N. Atarshchikova,

M.V. Baiteeva, M.A. Belyaev, Y.Y. Vetyutnev, D.A. Gavrilov, A.N.N. Germashinova, I.P. Germashinova, A.I. Ovchinnikov, A.E. Pisarevskii, R.A. Romashov, E.N. Tonkov, L.A. Kharitonov and others.) In the following years, issues of understanding and interpretation from the point of view of hermeneutic procedures became the subject of special research in various fields of law (V.M. Baranov, M.N. Amelchenko, T.A. Levchenkova, I.A. Kravets, S.L. Sergevnin, V.V. Suslov), including criminal law (Yu.V. Golik, Z.A. Zaginei, V. N. Neshataev, O. V. Pycheva).

The functional content of understanding is considered in three aspects: physiological, mental and socio-legal. In the qualification of crime and punishment, it is indicated that the interpretation is expressed in the understanding of the essence of the criminal event that occurred within the framework of a specific criminal-legal situation and the meaning of the Criminal Code norm applied to this event. Understanding and interpreting the factual circumstances of the case is a direct and integral part of the process of qualifying the crime.

At the same time, the understanding and interpretation of the factual circumstances of the case and the meaning of the criminal law norm is provided by special hermeneutic methods, among which "pre-understanding" ("pre-sentence") and "hermeneutic framework" are important. At the beginning of pre-trial proceedings, a "preliminary understanding" can serve as a preliminary ruling. The investigator's perception and understanding of the initial information obtained at the stage of criminal investigation allows him to make predictions: to form a version of the classification of the crime.

Within the hermeneutic paradigm of knowledge, the process of understanding has a circular structure. In a complete and adequate context, the meaning of the norm of the Criminal Code can be determined only in relation to a specific criminal-legal situation. At the same time, the emerging criminal-legal situation can be perceived and understood only with the help of the norms of the Criminal Code and other components of legal reality (principles, legal consciousness, legal rules of judicial practice, etc.).

From the point of view of the hermeneutic-phenomenological approach, the process of qualifying crime and punishment is considered not as a simple mental operation of the subject of law enforcement to compare the signs of a crime with the composition of the signs of a crime, but as a single process aimed at comparing the signs of a crime, hermeneutic procedures exists and develops in three.

The main problem of crime and punishment is related to morality. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to organize wide promotion of moral culture, moral

concepts and norms in the society. This can be the reason for the reduction of crimes in the society, at least partially. In addition, it should be said that as long as citizens of any country have a wide range of knowledge about moral norms and concepts, the number of negative incidents related to crime in this country can also decrease sharply.

The idea of phenomenology about the intentional attitude of our mind to the surrounding reality expands the field of hermeneutics and allows us to consider hermeneutic procedures and methods in relation not only to understanding and interpreting the text of the law, but also to determining the legal framework.

The hermeneutic procedures "understanding - interpretation - application" in their trinity form the philosophical basis of the cognitive process, and in the context of the qualification of the crime, it becomes the epistemological formula "understanding - interpretation - application", which is actually the process of applying the law under consideration. is alpha and omega.

CONCLUSION

In the process of qualifying crime and punishment, especially during the collection and evaluation of factual data, the dialectical method is leading. At the same time, one cannot ignore the changes taking place in the methodology of modern knowledge, which provide an opportunity to understand and explain the phenomena of social life based on the use of other methods. The achievements of philosophical hermeneutics and phenomenology are of special scientific interest within the framework of understanding modern methodological approaches to understanding the legal reality, which includes the crime phenomenon.

Summarizing the achievements of historically formed hermeneutic sciences and the individual ideas of philosophers, hermeneutics and phenomenology provide a universal conceptual and categorical apparatus that can be used in many areas of cognitive activity, including the process of qualifying crime according to tasks, and criminal-legal regulation.

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